

Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital heAlth Technology dEsiGn In sub saharan afriCa (STRATEGIC)

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Executive Summary:

The integration of digital health technologies (DHTs) into healthcare systems in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) presents significant opportunities for improving clinical research and trials. However, the successful implementation of these technologies requires comprehensive training and capacity building among key stakeholders, including National Ethics Committees (NECs), National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs), investigators, and community participants. This report identifies critical gaps and specific training requirements across various themes to enhance ethical oversight and regulatory compliance related to DHTs based on findings from the desk review of relevant standard operating procedures (SOPs), policies, and guidelines related to DHTs, as well as interviews with members of NECs and NRAs. The objective was to identify existing strengths, gaps, and training needs within these institutions to ensure they are equipped to address emerging ethical concerns associated with DHTs. This document is an interim report and not the final training needs assessment. Data collection is still in progress, with additional desktop reviews, interviews, focus group discussions, and online surveys planned to further refine the findings. Key findings highlight the need for training in understanding different DHTs, including electronic data capture systems, telemedicine, and artificial intelligence. There is also a pressing need for comprehensive training on legal frameworks and ethical guidelines associated with health research protocols using DHTs to ensure that stakeholders are well-informed and capable of navigating the complexities introduced by these innovations.

This report also underscores the importance of targeted training for secretariat staff within NECs and NRAs, focusing on effective navigation of protocol submission platforms and tracking mechanisms to enhance operational efficiency. The findings indicate a need for structured training materials that provide clear guidelines on ethical and regulatory issues specific to DHTs. This includes developing resources that empower local trainers to deliver culturally relevant education tailored to the unique contexts of SSA countries. The report emphasizes that addressing these training needs is crucial for enhancing ethical oversight and regulatory compliance related to DHTs in SSA.

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DHTs	Digital Health Technologies
EDCTP	European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership
EUREC	European Network of Research Ethics Committees
GHS	Ghana Health Service
LETS	Université de Yaoundé
LUMSA	Libera Università degli Studi Maria Ss. Assunta di Roma
NECs	National Ethics Committees
NRAs	National Regulatory Authorities
RDD	Research and Development Division
STRATEGIC	Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital health Technology dEsiGn In subsaharan afriCa
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
UoN	University of Nottingham
UEM	Universidade Eduardo Mondlane

Introduction

In recent years, the integration of digital health technologies has become a transformative force in enhancing healthcare delivery and clinical research across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). The World Health Organization's Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025 underscores the critical importance of these technologies such as mobile health (mHealth), electronic health records, telemedicine, and artificial intelligence in improving health outcomes in the region (WHO, 2020). However, this rapid adoption brings forth significant ethical, regulatory and legal challenges that necessitate careful consideration and robust governance frameworks (WHO, 2020).

Institutions responsible for providing ethical and legal guidance in health research are the National Ethics Committees (NECs), Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) and National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs). National Ethics Committees are responsible for the ethical oversight of research involving human subjects conducted at the national level while the IRBs focus on local oversight at the institutional level. NRAs are responsible for ensuring compliance with national regulations and laws governing research, drugs, and medical devices. Therefore, implications of digital health technologies in health research and clinical trial fall within the mandate of these institutions. To fulfil this mandate, it is needful for regulatory authorities and ethics committees to have the needed capacity to understand various digital health technologies and the regulatory and ethics issues that emanate from their use in health research. Understanding the capacity of these stakeholders is essential for developing effective training programmes that enhance their ability to review clinical research studies associated with digital health.

The STRATEGIC project aims to identify existing strengths, gaps, and training needs within these institutions, ensuring that they are equipped to address emerging ethical concerns. This report seeks to highlight these for needed capacity building among NECs and NRAs to effectively govern the integration of digital health technologies into clinical research and practice. These training needs, when addressed, can enhance ethical and legal oversight and promote responsible innovation that aligns with the values and principles of diverse communities across Sub-Saharan Africa. The purpose of this report is to detail the identified knowledge and skills gap of members of NRAs, NECs and IRBs.

Methodology

The first phase of the research started with an effort to identify and map the existing landscape of NECs and NRAs; existing and active committees; contact persons; their websites, available documents published by these committees (policies, regulations, Standard operating procedures –SOPs etc). English speaking partners (GHS, UoN) were tasked to identify and map the NECs and NRAs in English speaking African countries; LETs was tasked with doing the same for French speaking countries whilst UEM had the responsibility of doing the same with Portuguese speaking countries.

One month of doing this revealed that;

- There is significant lack of information (documents, policies and SOPs) on NECs and NRAs online including lack of website
- Available lists of NECs online (e.g a list from WHO) were old and many of the website links were not working
- Identified contacts (emails and phone numbers) were not going through

- The above findings led to a change in direction; rather than use the review to identify the documents to review and the stakeholders to interview; a decision was made to use the interviews to inform the review. Stakeholders were then selected from identifiable Ethics review boards (with local, institutional or national) in different countries of Africa.

To identify and communicate with the NRAs, NECs and IRBs across Sub-Saharan Africa, the GHS project coordinator and member of the consortium were tasked to conduct an online search of the NRAs, NECs and IRBs. The search was to identify the contact details (phone number, email address and name of institution and contact person). Phone calls and emails were used as follow-up to schedule the interviews. Additionally, personal connections were used to gain access to the contact details of the selected institutions. An excel template was developed and populated based on the findings from the search.

After populating the excel template a one-day online workshop was conducted by GHS to decide on the interview guide all research assistants in partner institutions. A semi-structured interview guide based on the phenomenon of interest that would be used for the interview was used for the workshop. The interviews were conducted in English, French and Portuguese. Each interview was transcribed and coded inductively based on the emerging themes. The interviews conducted in French and Portuguese were translated to English. Data collection officially started in October 2024.

The interviews aimed to gather first-hand insights into:

- The current regulatory and ethical oversight capacities of NECs and NRAs and challenges they face in reviewing and regulating digital health technologies for clinical trials and research.
- Existing training opportunities and resource gaps.
- Emerging ethical concerns, such as privacy, data security, and sociocultural sensitivities.
- Recommendations for tailored training to strengthen ethical and regulatory competencies.

There were many challenges this research process faced. They include;

Language Barrier

There are about four different languages mainly spoken in countries in Sub Saharan Africa. These are English, French, Portugues, and Arabic. Some countries speak more than one language for instance, Cameroon has French and English as their official languages. Allocating countries to partners was based on the existing language barrier as well as getting data collectors who will speak multiple languages for the interviews.

Difficulty of getting Contact details

The contact numbers identified on the institution's websites were either not correct, old numbers or individual contacts (these individuals were no longer staff of the institution). Additionally, some emails sent either bounced back or not responded to.

Request for specific country-based ethical clearance

Some of the identified potential participants declined to participate in the study because we had not obtained ethical approval from their respective countries. These countries included Sierra Leone and Liberia. In addition to the ethics approvals from Ghana and UoN, we obtained ethics approvals from Cameroon and Mozambique before interviews were conducted. This process delayed the interviews.

Non-existence of NRAs and NECs in some countries

Some of the countries contacted did not have either NRAs or NECs.

Skepticism of receiving fraudulent calls

Some of the potential participants contacted were hesitant to respond due to skepticism of receiving fraudulent calls. Thus, some either refused to provide any information or requested further communication via WhatsApp for record keeping.

The above challenges delayed the data landscape mapping phase of the project including delaying the data collection efforts. That is why this research is still ongoing. However, we have so far conducted 19 interviews in 7 countries. 10 of these interviews have so far been transcribed and analysed.

Qualitative Management and Analysis

A codebook was developed using the interview guides and inductively using emerging themes as well as the objectives of the study to guide the coding of transcripts. Data analysed thematically, focusing on key emerging themes and sub-themes that cut across various respondent groups. Qualitative data was analysed using NVivo 14 to categorize text in the transcripts based on the codebook and well as an excel template.

Data Management: All the interviews were audio recorded. The audio files were transcribed verbatim and word-processed using Microsoft Word. The researchers validated the transcripts by listening to a sample of the audio recordings to improve the quality of the transcripts.

Data Analysis: Thematic analysis method was used to analyse the qualitative data. The researchers first step was to read through all the transcripts to get a thorough overview of the content before examining individual items. A coding frame was developed using the interview guide in addition to codes identified from reading the transcripts, thus applying a combination of inductive and deductive approaches to identify and develop codes. The codes were independently applied to each transcript by two individual coders. A data interpretation meeting was held by the GHS team to reach a consensus on the themes identified.

Desktop research

Following the interviews, a desktop review was conducted. The documents were identified through the interviews and initial scoping of the websites of identified NECs and NRAs. The documents identified were then analysed using thematic analysis. Basically, grey literature from these institutions, ethics bodies, and regulatory agencies are being reviewed. For analysis, key themes such as governance structures, ethical review processes, regulatory challenges, and training gaps will be identified. There will then be the categorisation of findings based on country-specific and regional insights.

Initial Findings from Interviews

Initial analysis of some of the interviews conducted show a number of training needs for NECs, NRAs, and IRBs. These findings emerge from the analysis of the 10 interviews from 1 NRA, 4 NECs, and 5 IRBs. The countries interviewed included Ghana, Liberia, Zimbabwe, Nigeria,

Ethiopia, and Cameroun. The themes that emerged from the interviews include;

Lack of awareness of how digital health technologies are used for clinical trial and research

Some of the participants acknowledged the need to build the capacity of staff to increase knowledge and awareness at the various levels of digital technologies used in health research. The training will enable them to understand the concept of emerging technologies, digital health technologies, the ethical implications of using such technologies, the challenges and literature available on them. They also expressed the willingness of the staff to receive the training needed. Here are some quotes to reflect this:

“There are staff within the institution that are willing to be trained in the utilization of these digital services and to provide these digital services or to assess them. We don't have it in our system, so there's no infrastructure for that. So, going to that, we will have to go through a process on how we begin to implement it” (KII with member_Clinical trail unit-LB)

“I haven't yet. It's something that we need to have. (KII with member_research council_ZIM)

“I'll talk about myself. I really need to understand digital health. Just the basics. I need one-on-one. Digital health one-on-one. So, I need to start from the beginning. What is it that we need? The ethics bits, I know it. So, I need the training in digital health. What are the pitfalls? What are the lessons learned from other countries? Is there literature? So, I'm a basic person. But like I said, I'll give you the name of our executive secretary” (KII with IRB member_research council_ZIM)

“But maybe the ethics classes that we usually have as part of some of these courses. But in terms of formal training, it has been a challenge. We are trying to take steps to overcome that. We recently organized one training session for member” (KII with member_National health research committee_NG)

“Yes, of course, there are training needs. I am an investigator and sometimes I may be a little bit exposed to some of these devices. But if I look at some of the members on the committee who may not even have heard of some of the devices before and its use and all that, I will say there is a lot of capacity that we need to build to be able to bring members at the same level to adequately review such protocols and be able to make decisions. You find that with some of those protocols you want to rely on some aspects. There have been some instances where some aspects have been involved in the review process to come and give some additional information on certain aspects because the members are not very competent enough to be able to... Say in rural areas like where we are and all that, we need to understand some of these specifics issues, ethical considerations when we are deploying some of these in trials, as an ethics committee, we would want to have some additional training on those aspects, we may want to look at the risks that are associated with the deployment of some of these digital platforms” (KII with IRB_KNRC_GH)

Other participants mentioned the need to educate researchers too.

“Hmm, yeah, I think even the researchers, okay, who also need such training needs so that when they submit their work, you know, everything is in place. Yeah, so the researchers must have this kind of training, training. And maybe the institution can maybe also plan the training needs for them, I mean, for the researcher, for the researchers. And the various institutions, the schools, the colleges, and must also be, I mean, have been as part of the academy, I mean, to train people on this. Yes”. (KII with member_Korle Bu ERC_GH)

Additionally, the narrative that emerged is that since ethics review entities have regular trianing sessions, training on how digital health technologies are used for clinical trials and research is

a critical one. As participants observed;

“They have to be trained. The ethics committee is trained regularly. So, you find that at our monthly meeting, we try to end the monthly meeting every month with a training session What is new? Or what do we need to revise? How do we assign risk categorization for pediatrics? What about digital health? What about big data? What about data sharing? You know, whatever. So, we are continually being trained, plans” (KII with IRB member_KHRC_GH)

“So, like I said, at the end of our monthly meetings, we could have it. In our 30-minute discussion where everyone is there. The chairperson, the executive secretary and us members will be there. So, we can arrange” (KII with member_research council_ZIM)

“So, I might say, for example, administrators. We should be, we should be trained, you know, to, I mean, address also with the challenges and then what goes into this electronic device, you know, in clinical trials, yeah. So, the head administrator is trained. And even though our reviewers have expertise, they should refer, I mean, courses, training might also be used”

(KII with member_Kole Bu REC_GH)

Lack of specialist trainings

Whilst some participants indicated that they receive regular training, some mentioned the lack of specialist training for staff. Some participants expressed that members do not usually get such opportunities despite their level of expertise and experience. It was reported that most of the training that the committee members have acquired overtime was through formal education and not specialized training based on the phenomenon of interest.

“In terms of training, I think that is really a challenge. We don't have a lot of training opportunities for ethics committee members. Most of the trainings have been through our own formal education either through master's level or PhD level and all that” (KII with IRB member_KHRC_GH)

“We need that training. We have a lot of graduates. We need to train, a lot of them” (KII with member_National health research committee_NG)

Lack of awareness of the ethical implications of digital health technologies in Clinical Trials and research

The need for training on the ethical implications of the use of digital health technologies was mentioned by some of the interview participants. A participant mentioned that such training should be specialized training and not general training on ethics.

Some of these quotes reflects this;

“They should be trained on what they are, why there's a need for research to be done on them, and also on the ethics surrounding their use” (KII with member_ERC-GHS_GH)

“I mean, of course, this would be specialized training, but the general training on ethics, I presume most likely the members would have already gone through that. But refreshers on ethics may help. And the new trainings in ethical reviews, specifically for these ones, are the ones I mentioned”. (KII with member_ERC-GHS_GH)

“Yeah. So, for you, digital technologies, again, particularly for clinical trial, clinical trial is another level of challenge. So, let's mention observational studies. Even for observational studies, the digital tool, getting an approval from Ethics Committee is not easy because of the challenge I mentioned. So, we are trying to produce a couple of documents on data sharing

and AI, reviewing AI tools. That's not approved yet, but they are still collecting input from various sources. Nationally, we don't have strong data. Recently, the parliament approved the individual data protection policy or just the proclamation. So that kind of thing is coming up now". (KII with member_Amar Hansa Research Institute_Ethiopia)

"Yeah, there is a huge need for training on digital health technologies and ethics and AI tools so that we can participate in development of these technologies and reviewing protocols optimally so that we can protect participants, we can direct the use of data for the intended purpose and also protect data when it's necessary. So these training courses are important because these digital technologies are being opportunities so we are not benefiting from these technologies because of lack of expertise and also technology. So there is a huge need for a few resources and expertise. So, we really need to strengthen the ethics committees. So, we have that new AI tool is coming up for ethics committee review of protocols". (KII with member_Amar Hansa Research Institute_Ethiopia)

"Well, so it should start from scratch to, I mean, how you develop the protocol and what should go in. So, for example, like I mentioned earlier, how to develop the consent forms, how to even develop a consent form. And then the need for a local DSMB. One of the challenges I forgot to mention is the need for a local DSMB. For example, for the foreign studies, you know, they submit, but when you ask them to develop a local DSMB, they thought they have their people who have knowledge in there. But we believe that there should be a local DSMB because they are on grounds and they know the terrain, so they should be able to correct if something goes wrong, yes". (KII with member Korle Bu ERC_GH)

"I think it remains a need in our department that we will be able to have a training on the evaluation of protocols that are related to digital technology in the health domain to be able to understand what we are looking for". (KII with member Division of Health Operations Research_Cameron)

The findings also showed participants' perceptions of the complex nature of DHTs in relation to their use and the need to build the capacity of both reviews and administrative staff of ethics review boards and committees. This complexity is often introduced by the addition of emerging technologies like AI.

"We also think that ethical issues with respect to digital technology are more challenging than generally the other issues because digital technology now requires maybe the use of the AIs. It requires the use of other complex information and communication technologies that are not being mastered by the personnels of the department. So maybe training in this will also be important. And maybe good clinical practices with the use of digital technologies will also be a good thing". (KII with member Division of Health Operations Research_Cameron)

Sustainability of Training

The need for periodic update of information was also mentioned due to frequent introduction of different emerging technologies in health research. Participants who are familiar with ethics of emerging technologies also require training to updated training given the expanding landscape of emerging technologies. This called for the need to upgrade the capacity of the members of the ethics board with respect to emerging technologies and their associated challenges in health research.

"There is always a training need, because every day emerging technologies come up, and there's always a need to upgrade the capacity of board members. So, you always have to know the way the technology emerges, or at the way the challenges are coming up, you need to upgrade your positioning of support if you want to train your board members on these issues"

(KII with member_NRA_FDA-_GH)

Infrastructural needs

A participant mentioned the need to build non-existing institutional infrastructure for assessing digital health technologies as well as the training to operate and maintain such infrastructure.

“We have to build a infrastructure and a system that would be able to take keep up with emerging technologies. We don't have that. So, we don't have a structure for digital technology. We don't have a system to put into place to make it operational and whatnot like that. Then, two, these digital technologies that are existing, developing them, we don't have it. So, we will need some of those tools to work with. And then, of course, like I earlier said, and the people would be trained for the uses of such work.” (KII with member_clinical trail unit_LB)

“Yeah. So, for you, digital technologies, again, particularly for clinical trial, clinical trial is another level of challenge. So, let's mention observational studies. Even for observational studies, the digital tool, getting an approval from Ethics Committee is not easy because of the challenge I mentioned. So, we are trying to produce a couple of documents on data sharing and AI, reviewing AI tools. That's not approved yet, but they are still collecting input from various sources. Nationally, we don't have strong data. Recently, the parliament approved the individual data protection policy or just the proclamation. So that kind of thing is coming up now”. (KII with member_Amar Hansa Research Institute_Ethiopia)

Lack of Clear policy documents on the evaluation/assessment

The participants mentioned the need to develop policy guidelines or documents that could regulate the introduction of digital health technologies in health research in general and clinical trial research/practice in particular. The guidelines could focus on the design, development and deployment of digital health technologies. They also advocated for the introduction of basic courses that could build their capacities in this regard.

“Something to help us to develop guidelines and regulations as it relates to research or policy documents. Because we don't have it, so introducing it would need to do more work on legal documents and such work. Those are other things that we need. And then, basic courses that can help us into some of these kinds of work” (KII with member_clinical trail unit_LB)

“...but we have our guidelines, the review, but we don't have a specific guideline on digital health technology.” (KII with member_Natioal health research committee_NG)

I don't think they're specific to digital health (KII with member_IRB_KHRC_GH)

“But we as an ethics body, we do not have a separate document on this very aspect, as far as I can remember. I can't remember coming across any document or policy on the deployment of these devices. I'm really trying to remember, but I can't.” (KII with member_IRB_KHRC_GH)

“But I also need to add something on the specific guidelines on the design of these digital platforms and how to deploy them and what to consider. And if these guidelines are there and ethics committees are trained adequately on these aspects, it will go a long way to fostering a better understanding of the review process. I think that will help” (KII with member_IRB_KHRC_GH)

“I don't think we have specifically for that. We need to work on that. We do have general guidelines” (KII with member_research council_ZIM)

“So, the ecosystem, when you assess, there is a huge gap in having the right documents and proclamations to cover data sharing and also for digital tools. So when you say digital tool,

again, I mentioned repeatedly about the data sharing because we understand that's the main thing which is important to approve the tools to be used. So clinical trial is another challenge because clinical trial involves randomization". (KII with member_Amar Hansa Research Institute_Ethiopia)

"So, the level of control and regularity review is higher than observational studies. So digital tool, clinical trial, so you see the challenge, further challenging encounter. So, I will say very few documents, but I will share with you if there are any". (KII with member_Amar Hansa Research Institute_Ethiopia)

"Yes, there are technologies which have been approved by our Ethics Committee. So, the Ethics Committee just expresses their concern because they review and approve based on the existing policies and standard operating procedures, despite the concerns they have. So, the more protocols are coming, the more challenges are coming. Otherwise, we are just reusing the existing SOPs. So, we are planning to develop and understand the WHO guidance on AI review so that we can adopt those things to our Ethics Committee". (KII with member_Amar Hansa Research Institute_Ethiopia)

"In the domain of health, it's actually challenging to be able to identify a guideline or a legal document or a regulatory instrument that takes into consideration digital health technology. But if we want to look at it, we will look at the regulation that has been put in place by the Ministry of Telecommunication, which concerns the protection of children. And it is with respect to the online collection of data from minors. So, it ensures that children are protected from being exploited online by those who are carrying out research. So, it's actually a general framework just to protect children that are carried out children online, but it does not really specify or limit it to the domain of health. But it precises ethical principles, the respect of consent, authorization, presentation of the objective of the study, and limits that maybe those who are minors, the research team or the PI should request for the authorization of the parents or the guidance". (KII with member Division of Health Operations Research_Cameron)

"...I think we should make it if you want to develop a guideline for digital technology, it will be important that it considers because as I said, we are dealing in the domain of health research. It will be important to develop a guideline that differentiates clearly digital technology used for data collection and digital technology used for healthcare delivery". (KII with member Division of Health Operations Research_Cameron)

Despite the need to provide essential context-based documents on DHT, a participant mentioned that there is a need for legal frameworks. However, these legal frameworks were within the domain of the government followed by other stakeholders.

"Yes. No, elaborating guidelines, we do not limit it to what the government wants. It starts with, first of all, what the government wants from the population. So, if the government is intending to regulate a domain, it is for the protection of the population. So how do we protect the population without getting involved with the population? So the different stakeholders, for example, if we are carrying out a regulation on healthcare, then those who are concerned with the protection of the patient, the association that are concerned with protection of the patients, association that are concerned with sick people, association that are concerned with different areas, respect to health, and then even those that are concerned with medication, the supply of medication, they are being considered. And then we bring in political actors also. We bring in economic factors because at one point in time also economic aspects can be involved. So, they do a general consultation. That's why we say with all stakeholders, that whoever we consider is important for the implementation of this project, that person is brought in". (KII with member Division of Health Operations Research_Cameron)

Although the findings showed the need for developing regulatory frameworks to guide

activities related to the phenomenon of interest, a participant mentioned the existence of general administrative guidelines that involve sanctions for researchers. Such administrative sanctions include suspension of authorization, closure of affiliated research institution, and withdrawal of license.

“There are two sanctions and there are penal sanctions that apply to this researcher. So, for administrative sanctions, the first is that there is a suspension of the authorization that the researcher has received. Secondly, besides suspension, there can be a closure of the researcher's structure or the institution of research. Besides the closure, there could also be a withdrawal of the license of this researcher. If it's a nurse, they can withdraw his license. They can suspend the license and all that. So, they can even cease, go to the extent of ceasing and destroying all the samples that were collected without the respect of these regulations. Besides these administrative sanctions, there are penal sanctions that involve fines and imprisonment that may go up to 10 or 20 years”. (KII with member Division of Health Operations Research_Cameron)

Initial Findings from desktop research

The documents reviewed consisted of SoPs, National code of health research ethics and guidelines. These findings further confirmed the lack of institutional or national policies and guidelines for digital health technologies in general and digital health technologies used for clinical trial research and practice in SSA. The analysis also confirms that some of the ethics review boards have regular monthly meetings that can be relied on for capacity building workshops. Additional findings from the document review include the following;

- Though some documents mention 'electronic' multiple times, these were not in the context of digital health technologies. Some of the documents primarily focus on guidelines for the establishment of food storage facilities. This is mainly because most of the NECs also double as Food and Drug Agencies.
- Others focused on guidelines for the authorization of clinical trials. The documents do not make reference to assessment of the use of digital health innovations such as Electronic Data Capture (EDC) Systems, Electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs), eConsent Platforms, Electronic Patient-Reported Outcomes (ePRO), Wearable Devices and Biosensors, Remote Monitoring and Telemedicine, Clinical Trial Management Systems (CTMS), Electronic Health Records (EHRs) Integration, Big Data and Advanced Analytics, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), Natural Language Processing (NLP). They document primarily focus on the Standard Operating Procedures for ethical review and monitoring of human research studies, with no references to technological innovations in research

Documents already reviewed

1. Guidelines for the Establishment of a Food Storage Facility, 21st May 2020 – Ghana;
2. Guideline for Authorization of Clinical Trials of Medicines, Food Supplements, Vaccines and Medical Devices in Ghana, 15th January 2024
3. National Health Research Ethics Committee: Guidelines of Ethics for Health Research in Tanzania, Second Edition 2009
4. SOP for National Health Research Ethics Committee, Nigeria, 2007
5. The South African Medical Research Council Human Research Ethics Committee: SOPs, 1st February 2023
6. SOP for Scientific Review of Proposals for Research with Humans Prior to submission to the SAMRC Research Ethics Committee, South Africa, 8th July 2021
7. Research Ethics Committee (UMI REC) guidelines and SOPs for Humanities and

Social Sciences Research (HSSR), Uganda, June 2023

Guidelines for the Establishment of a Food Storage Facility, 21st May 2020 – Ghana

Ongoing work

In the next six months, the interviews will be completed and analysed, and more SOPs will be analysed to get a comprehensive view of the training needs in SSA. These will feed into the co-creation workshops in WP3 as well as the development of the training materials in WP5.

Conclusion

This report gives an interim assessment of findings from interviews and desktop reviews. Findings mainly indicate that there is a general lack of understanding of digital health technologies; particularly emerging and advanced DHTs. There is also a lack of comprehension of the ethical, regulatory and legal implications of DHTs for various stakeholders, particularly Ethics Committees and National Regulatory Authorities. Moreover, there is the need to institute structures for training, which involves taking into account emerging DHTs and collaborating with relevant institutional stakeholders. Finally, there was a call for capacity building in developing guidelines on reviewing health research protocols relating to DHTs

Appendix A: List of Countries and Institutions Interviewed

Country	Name of Institution	Type of Institution	Language used for interview
Ghana	Ghana Health Service Ethics Committee	NEC	English
Ghana	Food and Drugs Authority	NRA	English
Ghana	Kintampo Health Research Centre IRB	IRB	English
Ghana	Korle Bu Teaching Hospital ERC	IRB	English
Liberia	Clinical trial unit	IRB	English
Zimbabwe	Medial Research council	NEC	English
Zimbabwe	Medical Research Council	NEC	English
Nigeria	National health research committee	NEC	English
Ethiopia	Armar Hansa Research Institute	IRB	English
Cameroun	Division of Health Operations Research	IRB	French